

СЕМАНТИЧЕСКИЕ МОДЕЛИ УСТОЙЧИВЫХ ЕДИНИЦ В РАССКАЗАХ

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Аннотация.

В статье будет рассматриваться непосредственно фразеологическая система в рассказах и пьесах А. П. Чехова «Вишневый сад», «Дядя Ваня», «Иванов», «Ионыч», «Женское счастье», «Лошадиная фамилия», «Медведь», «Рассказ неизвестного человека», «Три года», «Три сестры» и др.

Ключевые слова.

А. П. Чехова, фразеология, негативной, иронической, манера, стилистической окраски, линия поведения, неискренность, выражение отчаяния, бессилия, невозможности, предпринять, затруднительно, безвыходно, положение...

SEMANTIC MODELS OF STABLE UNITS IN A.P. CHEKHOV

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Annotation.

The article will directly consider the phraseological system in the stories and plays by A.P. Chekhov "The Cherry Orchard", "Uncle Vanya", "Ivanov", "Ionych", "Women's Happiness", "Horse Family", "Bear", "The Story of an Unknown Man", "Three Years", "Three Sisters", etc.

Key words.

A.P. Chekhov, phraseology, negative, ironic, manner, stylistic coloring, line of conduct, insincerity, expression of despair, impotence, impossibility, undertaking, difficult, hopeless, situation...

In the works of A.P. Chekhov, we find the following phraseological combinations, for example:

1. "And, obviously, all the good talk we have is only to avert the eyes of ourselves and others." (The Cherry Orchard)

Avert your eyes - divert attention, mislead.

2. "I'm good, what a fool I dumped!" (The Cherry Orchard)

Play the fool - do stupid things, do not do the right thing.

This phraseological unit is used with a pronounced expressive coloring (negative, ironic).

3. "Show off - create a false impression of yourself, presenting it better than it actually is.

4. "Beauty is not forever given! Ten years will pass, you yourself want to walk with a pavoy and throw dust in the eyes of gentlemen officers, but it will be too late. (Bear)

5. "You do not know how to behave in a female society." (Bear)

Keep yourself - keep a certain way, about manners.

6. "I remember, the last name is horse, and which one was knocked out of my head ..." (Horse last name)

It was knocked out of my head - to suddenly forget something.

7. "You don't believe in conspiracies, but I experienced it myself. Although you do not believe, why not send? Hands after all not fall off from this. (horse name)

Hands do not fall off (simple) - it will not be difficult to do something.

From the point of view of expressive - stylistic coloring, this phraseological unit refers to colloquial vocabulary.

8. "My husband is jealous, this is Othello, but we will try to behave in such a way that he will not notice anything." (Ionych)

To behave is to act in any way, to adhere to a certain line of behavior.

9. "An hour later he was still sitting in the same place, staring at the security deposit." (Life's troubles)

Goggle (stare) - stare, stubbornly look at someone.

10. "Producing nervously ill children is a crime." (For service)

To give birth is to give life to someone. [11, p. 362]

11. "If she had not been lazy and pulled herself together, then a wonderful singer would have come out of her." (Jumper)

Pull yourself together - become collected, active.

12. "Annie came out of the hut and God bless her feet, wherever her eyes look." (Incident)

Wherever the eyes look - without a specific direction, without choosing the path, wherever you want, wherever you want to go.

13. "Not by night, be it said, it's a sin to guess such people, there was a filthy old man." (Happiness)

Don't be told at night - it's not the time, you shouldn't say, mention.

14. "Her nose seemed longer than it used to be, and there was not a blood on her face, despite the cold." (Three years)

Not a blood in his face - very pale.

15. "Your insincerity is both natural and in the order of things." (Misfortune)

In the order of things - usually, normally.

16. "I love you, I love you to the point that I got off track, quit my business and loved ones, forgot my god!" (Misfortune)

Get out of the rut - stop leading a familiar lifestyle.

A large number of phraseological fusions are also observed in the stories of A.P. Chekhov. So, phraseological fusions are such semantically indivisible combinations of words, the general meaning of which is not motivated by the meaning of the components.

1. "As soon as I see a poetic retribution even from a distance, my calves begin to cramp from anger. Just at least shout the guard. (Bear)

Although the guard scream - an expression of despair, powerlessness, the inability to do anything to get out of a difficult or hopeless situation.

2. "Well, gentlemen? The third hour, it's time and honor to know. (The Cherry Orchard)

It's time and honor to know - it's time to stop (doing) something, time to leave, retire.

3. "I fell in love like that, from the bay, without even knowing and not knowing what kind of person I am." (In the country)

From the bay-floundering - suddenly, for no apparent reason, for no reason; thoughtlessly (to act, to do something).

4. "So why the hell are you climbing with advice if you forgot? the general got angry. (horse name)

Damn it (simple) - an exclamation expressing indignation, indignation, surprise, admiration or annoyance.

5. "Listen, Matvey, you will agree to the point that you, sorry for the expression, will be taken to the yellow house." (Ivanov)

Yellow House (obsolete) - a hospital for the mentally ill, an insane asylum.

6. "Walks or talks, but it's written on his forehead: I'm an honest person!" (Ivanov)

It is written on the forehead - you can immediately see, clearly, notice something to everyone in the appearance of a person.

7. "This means, I think, the general wanted to calculate her, and she took advantage of the fact that there were no witnesses and minted it in full." (Woman's happiness)

To all crusts (simple) - very strongly (scold, scold, smash).

8. "- Whoever cheats on his wife or husband, that means an unfaithful person, he can also cheat on the fatherland! "Shut up the fountain, Waffle!" (Uncle Ivan)

Shut up the fountain! (rude - simple) - shut up, shut up, shut your mouth.

From the point of view of expressive - stylistic coloring, this phraseological unit refers to roughly - vernacular vocabulary.

9. "He can't afford to live in the city." (Uncle Ivan)

Unaffordable - beyond the means, too expensive for anyone.

10. "The settlers interpret that this area was the bottom of the sea at that time, and that the Gilyaks now find things from ships on it." (Sakhalin island)

At the time of ona (obsolete) - once, once, a very long time ago.

11. "Why should I and these unfortunates sit here for everyone, like scapegoats?" (Ward №6)

A scapegoat is a person who is blamed for someone else's guilt, responsibility for others.

12. "Then you drank blood from people, and now they will drink from you." (Ward №6)

Drink blood (simple) - torment, oppress someone, mock, mock someone.

13. "I have pride. Not everyone is pleased to be the fifth wheel in a cart. (Log)

The fifth wheel in a cart is an extra, unnecessary person in any business.

14. "They only eat, drink, sleep, then die ... and, in order not to become stupid with boredom, diversify their lives with nasty gossip, vodka, cards! .. and the spark of God goes out in them." (Three sisters)

God's spark (obsolete) - noble impulses of feelings, high aspirations; giftedness, talent, outstanding abilities.

15. "They didn't neglect the person, they took him into the house and now he, I suppose, prays to God for you." (Three years)

To pray to God (obsolete) - to express one's deep gratitude to someone, to be infinitely grateful.

16. "It's a pity, we live with you not so hot." (Three years)

Not so hot - not very, not particularly good.

17. "However, jokes aside, the brother resolved, I brought one article, a test of the pen, so to speak, and brought you to show." (Three years)

A test of the pen is the first literary experience.

18. "Cool old man," muttered Panteley. - what a cool trouble! (Steppe)

Trouble (fear, horror) what (simple) - very, extremely (strong, brave, evil).

19. "But Anyutka is a girl, not a miss. For nothing that she's a fool, but she thought up something that not everyone and the literate will jump into the mind." (Incident)

Not a miss - dexterous, quick-witted, will not miss his own.

20. "I didn't think, now the public will look at me with all their eyes. Where would you hide? (1st class passenger)

Look through all eyes - peer intently somewhere, looking forward to the appearance of someone; look at someone or something for a long time or incessantly.

21. "Baba ... nasty, poisonous, looks like Satan. As soon as he starts shouting at someone, as he raises a screech, so at least endure the saints. (Woman's happiness)

Even endure the saints - there is no strength to endure anything; unbearable, unbearable for others.

After analyzing phraseological fusions, we can conclude that the reasons why we attribute these units to phraseological fusions are varied: obsolete words included in their composition, this is syntactic inseparability between the components of phrases. In many cases, the connection between the meaning of each of the components of phraseological fusion and its meaning as a whole is lost.

A significant place in the stories of A.P. Chekhov is occupied by phraseological units. The main feature of phraseological units is figurativeness.

1. "On Thursday I was in the district court, well, the company agreed, a conversation began about this, about this, the fifth or tenth." (The Cherry Orchard)

Fifth - tenth - an expression used instead of a detailed enumeration, the name of something.

2. "- I broke the saucer ... - this is good." (Cherry Orchard) (Women's Happiness)

For good - an expression that portends good; to success, luck.

3. "Recently, the first snow fell, and everything in nature was under the rule of this first snow." (fit)

Under the influence - under the influence, under the influence or impression.

4. "But one must have a head on one's shoulders," said Orlov, "one must reason." (The story of an unknown person)

To have a head on your shoulders - to be smart, quick-witted, reasonable.

5. "Before we, grimy, get out on the real road, a lot of our brother will lay down the bones." (Three years)

Our brother is us and our kind.

6. "I just must be stupid and nailed around the corner with a bag." (Blank case)

From around the corner he was nailed with a bag - with oddities, a silly person. This phraseological phrase has a pronounced negative connotation.

7. "They loved to kill a fly (simple). It used to be impossible to drive past the tavern." (Incident)

To kill a fly - to drink intoxicating, to peck.

From the point of view of expressive - stylistic coloring, this phraseological unit belongs to colloquial vocabulary. This expression is not characteristic of literary speech.

8. "They (the French) need to peel the sausages and nothing else, but Germany, brother, does not have the same music." (Ivanov)

Not that (other, different) music (simple) - not at all, something special; otherwise (went, something will go).

9. "Both the cherry orchard and the land must be leased out for summer cottages, do it now, as soon as possible - the auction is on the nose." (The Cherry Orchard)

On the nose (simple) - very soon, in the very near future, something is about to happen or come.

This phraseological unit belongs to colloquial vocabulary.

10. "If she is here without a husband and without acquaintances," Gurov thought, "then it would not be superfluous to get to know her." (Lady with a dog)

Not superfluous - not bad, useful to do something.

11. "From morning to night, everyone is on their feet, I don't know peace, but at night you lie under the covers and are afraid that they won't drag you to the patient." (Uncle Ivan)

On the legs - 1) in a standing position; 2) in the waking state, getting up from sleep; 3) in chores, worries, at work, without sitting down, without lying down; 4) healthy, not sick; 5) not going to bed, without sickness, not sick; 5) not going to bed, without bed rest (to endure an illness, to get sick).

Analyzing the listed options for the use of this phraseological unit, it should be noted, based on the context, that in this case the writer used the phraseological unit "on his feet" in the story - in chores, worries, at work, without sitting down, without lying down.

12. "In order for me to become a prince or a count, I need to conquer the whole world, and some, God forgive me, Varenka or Katenka, the milk on my lips has not dried up, twists a train in front of the count, squints her eyes - that's your Excellency ..." (Women's happiness)

The milk on the lips has not dried up (simple) - someone is still very young and inexperienced.

This phraseological unit is a colloquial expression, not typical of literary speech, which the author apparently uses to create a special effect.

13. "For three days, things fell out of his hands, he didn't eat, didn't sleep, but when a rumor reached him that Ekaterina Ivanovna had gone to Moscow to enter the conservatory, he calmed down and healed as before." (Ionych)

To fall out of hand - not to succeed, not to get along due to the lack of an appropriate mood, strength, desire.

13. "... I found only thirty-nine peasants, and all of them were far from the intention to take root; everyone was going to the mainland." (Sakhalin island)

Take root - 1) firmly, permanently settle somewhere, acquire a household; 2) acquire special strength, become permanent, take root. About feelings, habits, phenomena, actions.

Based on the context in which this expression is used, it can be assumed that the phraseological unit "take root" is used in the sense of "settle somewhere for a long time".

Thus, having analyzed phraseological units, we come to the conclusion that the main criterion that unites all phraseological units is the motivation of the whole meaning of a phraseological unit, the values of its components. Having analyzed the phraseological units from the point of view of the semantic solidarity of the components found in the stories of A.P. Chekhov, we can conclude that phraseological units and fusions significantly prevail over phraseological combinations.

In the course of the analysis of the works of A.P. Chekhov, phraseological expressions were also distinguished:

1. "It used to turn away to the window, whisper, spit - and like a hand! The strength is given to him so much ..." (Horse surname)

And as if by hand (removed) - instantly, immediately passed without a trace (about malaise, illness, feelings of experience).

2. "There are few good people, but God forbid how many villains and murderers!" (restless guest)

God forbid how much! - a lot, a lot.

3. "Dear grandfather, do God's mercy, take me from here home to the village, there is no way for me ..." (Vanka)

Do God's favor (obsolete) - an expression of an intensified or humiliated request.

4. "I'll rub tobacco for you," he continued, "... and if anything, then flog me like a sidorov's goat." (Vanka)

Slash like a Sidor's goat (simple) - cruelly, mercilessly.

5. "Every dog in Saratov knows him," said the clerk. - If you please write, Your Excellency, to the city of Saratov, therefore ... "(Horse surname)

Every dog knows (simple) - everyone, everyone, anyone knows (about a person).

6. "I fiddled all day, didn't sit down, there was no poppy dew in my mouth." (Uncle Ivan)

There was no poppy dew in the mouth - no one had eaten anything.

7. "- Nanny, how much has passed, how do we know each other? - How many? God bless the memory. (Uncle Ivan)

God grant memory - an expression of desire, an effort to remember something.

8. "It was especially that pigeons flew over the fire in smoke and in the tavern, where they still did not know about the fire, they continued to sing and play the harmonica, as if nothing had happened." (guys)

As if nothing had happened - as if nothing happened, did not happen.

Thus, having considered the phraseological expressions used by A.P. Chekhov, it can be noted that their role is undoubtedly great, since they give special expressiveness and piquancy to a work of art.

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